

THE ROLE OF SOCIOLINGUISTIC COMPETENCE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF A1 LEVEL STUDENTS IN ENGLISH LESSONS

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Abstract. This article examines the role of sociolinguistic competence in developing the communicative competence of A1 level students in English lessons. Important aspects of developing sociolinguistic competence are analyzed and various methods are proposed.

Keywords: sociolinguistic competence, types, styles, culture, tradition.

It is known that the main purpose of education in the competence-based foreign language learning method is to form the scientific ability of learners, in which, through the development of communicative competence, the learner is expected to focus on developing the skills of applying the theoretical and practical knowledge acquired during the lesson to everyday life. This goal can be achieved by using exercises aimed at the formation of linguistic, pragmatic, socio-linguistic and strategic competencies, which are the components of communicative competence, in the course of the lesson, and by forming these competencies in the minds of language learners. The purpose of developing the above-mentioned competences in students in the English language learning program of comprehensive schools is included in the state education standard. Formation of sociolinguistic competence, which is one of the components of communicative competence, is considered one of the important tasks in this regard.

Among our local researchers M.Sh Ruzmetova in her scientific work, defines sociolinguistic competence as follows: "Sociolinguistic competence is the knowledge of the customs, traditions, rituals and other national-cultural features of the country in which one lives, as well as the language of each people, nation, through topics related to everyday life, social life, education and culture. It refers to the ability of its representatives to present their thoughts orally and in writing, in accordance with their unique established customs and images" [3]. In his work, the researcher emphasized the technologies of developing linguistic and sociolinguistic competences based on communicative-cognitive and communicative-cumulative methods in teaching English to A-1 students.

Sociolinguistic competence is an awareness of the way of life, customs, culture, geographic features and moral norms of the society whose language is being studied, their unique standard and substandard (non-standard) speaking style, dialect, non-verbal actions, fixed combinations, expressions used in conversation etiquette of different age groups and the ability to use words and phrases in a specific context in both written and oral speech is understood. In short, the ability to communicate English to English and French to French can be seen as a sign of the level of sociolinguistic competence [1].

Informal	Formal
<i>Check</i>	<i>Verify</i>
<i>Start/ Begin</i>	<i>Commence</i>
<i>Get</i>	<i>Receive</i>
<i>Dealwith</i>	<i>Handle</i>
<i>Tell</i>	<i>Inform</i>
<i>Fight</i>	<i>Combat</i>
<i>Use/Eat</i>	<i>Consume</i>

For example, English language learners, especially A-1 level school students, should be able to distinguish between formal and informal English speech units, when and where to use them. Lack of knowledge of oral and written register can cause misunderstanding in conversation or written communication. Let's distinguish between formal and informal language units (table 1):

Table 1. Formal and informal language units

Non-verbal communication is also of special importance in the speech process, each nation has its own non-verbal communication style. In this case, mainly sensory organs, eyes, lips, ears, facial expressions and gestures play the main role. Familiarity with the non-verbal communication style of the society whose language is being studied is one of the main tasks in the formation of sociolinguistic competence.

Formation of sociolinguistic competences of students of level A-1 motivates them to learn more about the culture of the language they are studying and to speak the language fluently using the correct units. This, in turn, ensures that in the future they will be able to communicate freely in the international arena with representatives of this nation or with representatives of other nations who can speak the same language. This is the main goal of the transition from the traditional translation method to the communicative language teaching method.

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